

Supporting information

Genomics of Carbon Atomic Chains

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1. ZiEU6 and ArEU6 (asymmetric junctions)

1.1. Total transmissions, with both ferromagnetically and antiferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S1. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZiES6, (g) ArES6. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively.

1.2. Spin up and down transmissions with antiferromagnetically-aligned edges

Figure S2. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZIEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZIES6, (g) ArES6. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients for spin up (red), down (blue) and total $T(E)$ with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively.

1.3. Spin densities with antiferromagnetically-aligned edges

Figure S3. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZiEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZiES6, (g) ArES6. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

1.4. Spin up and down transmissions with ferromagnetically-aligned edges

Figure S4. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZiES6, (g) ArES6. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

1.5. Spin densities with ferromagnetically-aligned edges

Figure S5. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZiEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZIES6, (g) ArES6. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

2. ZiEU6 and ArEU6 (symmetric junctions)

2.1. Total transmissions, with both ferromagnetically and antiferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S6. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZiES6, (g) ArES6. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively.

2.2. Spin up and down transmissions, with antiferromagnetically-aligned edges.

Figure S7. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZiES6, (g) ArES6. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

2.3. Spin densities with antiferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S8. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZIES6, (g) ArES6. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of $(\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow})$. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

2.4. Spin up and down transmissions of symmetric junctions with ferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S9. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZiES6, (g) ArES6. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

2.5. Spin densities of symmetric junctions with ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S10. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIEU6, (c) ArEU6, (e) ZIES6, (g) ArES6. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

3. ZiEU5 and ArEU5 (unsaturated terminal rings)

3.1. Total transmissions, with ferromagnetically align or antiferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S11. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiEU5, (c) ArEU5, (e) ZiES5, (g) ArES5. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively.

3.2. Spin up and down transmissions with antiferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S12. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZIEU5, (c) ArEU5, (e) ZIES5, (g) ArES5. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

3.3. Spin densities with antiferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S13. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIEU5, (c) ArEU5, (e) ZIES5, (g) ArES5. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

3.4. Spin up and down transmissions with ferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S14. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZIEU5, (c) ArEU5, (e) ZIES5, (g) ArES5. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

3.5. Spin densities with ferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S15. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIEU5, (c) ArEU5, (e) ZIES5, (g) ArES5. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

4.1. Total transmissions, with both ferromagnetically and antiferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S16. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZnEu5, (c) ArEu5, (e) ZnES5, (g) ArES5, (i). (b), (d), (f), (h), (j) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g), (i) respectively.

4.2. Spin up and down transmissions with antiferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S17. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiEU5, (c) ArEU5, (e) ZiES5, (g) ArES5, (i) ArES5. (b), (d), (f), (h), (j) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g), (i) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

4.3. Spin densities with antiferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S18. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIEU5, (c) ArEU5, (e) ZIES5, (g) ArES5. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

4.4. Spin up and down transmissions with ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S19. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZIEU5, (c) ArEU5, (e) ZIES5, (g) ArES5, (i) ArES5. (b), (d), (f), (h), (j) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g), (i) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

4.5. Spin densities with ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S20. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIEU5, (c) ArEU5, (e) ZIES5, (g) ArES5. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively.

5. ZiOS6, ArOS6, ZiOU6 and ArOU6

5.1. Total transmissions with antiferromagnetically or ferromagnetically aligned edges.

Figure S21. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiOU6, (c) ArOU6, (e) ZiOS6, (g) ArOS6. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

5.2. Spin up and down with antiferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S22. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiOU6, (c) ArOU6, (e) ZiOS6, (g) ArOS6. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

5.3. Spin densities with antiferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S23. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIOU6, (c) AROU6, (e) ZIOS6, (g) AROS6. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

5.4. Spin up and down transmissions with ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S24. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiOU6, (c) ArOU6, (e) ZiOS6, (g) ArOS6. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

5.5. Spin densities with ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S25. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIOU6, (c) AROU6, (e) ZIOS6, (g) AROS6. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of $(\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow})$. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

6. ZiOU5 and ArOU5 (unsaturated 5-membered terminal rings)

6.1. Total transmissions with antiferromagnetically or ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S26. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiOU5, (c) ArOU5, (e) ZiOS5, (g) ArOS5. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively.

6.2. Spin up and down transmissions with antiferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S27. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiOU5, (c) ArOU5, (e) ZiOS5, (g) ArOS5. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

6.3. Spin densities with antiferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S28. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIOU5, (c) AROU5, (e) ZIOS5, (g) ARoS5. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

6.4. Spin up and down transmissions with ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S29. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZIOU5, (c) ArOU5, (e) ZIOS5, (g) ArOS5. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

6.5. Spin densities with ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S30. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIOU5, (c) AROU5, (e) ZIOS5, (g) AROS5. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of $(\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow})$. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

7. ZiOU5 and ArOU5 (saturated terminal rings)

7.1. Total transmissions with antiferromagnetically or ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S31. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiOU5, (c) ArOU5, (e) ZiOS5, (g) ArOS5. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

7.2. Spin up and down with antiferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S32. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) $ZiOU_5$, (c) $ArOU_5$, (e) $ZiOS_5$, (g) $ArOS_5$. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

7.3. Spin densities with antiferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S33. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIOU5, (c) ArOU5, (e) ZIOS5, (g) ArOS5. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

7.4. Spin up and down transmissions with ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S34. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiOU5, (c) ArOU5, (e) ZiOS5, (g) ArOS5. (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

7.5. Spin densities with ferromagnetically aligned edges

Figure S35. Spin densities ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$) for (a) ZIOU5, (c) AROU5, (e) ZIOS5, (g) AROS5. Blue and red correspond to positive and negative isosurfaces of ($\rho_{\uparrow} - \rho_{\downarrow}$). (b), (d), (f), (h) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (c), (e), (g) respectively. Dotted red (blue) lines are spin up (down) transmissions. Total transmission is shown by black line.

8. Local density of states (LDOS)

8.1. ZiEU6 and ZiES6

Figure S36. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiEU6, (e) ZiES6. (b), (f) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (e) respectively. (c), (d), (g), (h) are the corresponding LDOS for energy range shown by dashed lines for (a), (e) respectively.

8.2. ArEU6 and ArES6

Figure S37. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ArEU6, (e) ArES6. (b), (f) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (e) respectively. (c), (d), (g), (h) are the corresponding LDOS for energy range shown by dashed lines for (a), (e) respectively.

8.3. ZiOU6 and ZiOS6

Figure S38. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ZiOU6, (e) ZiOS6. (b), (f) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (e) respectively. (c), (d), (g), (h) are the corresponding LDOS for energy range shown by dashed lines for (a), (e) respectively.

8.4. ArOU6 and ArOS6

Figure S39. All carbon junctions formed by two graphene electrodes connected to the relaxed atomic structure of (a) ArOU6, (e) ArOS6. (b), (f) are the corresponding DFT transmission coefficients with the antiferromagnetic and the ferromagnetic spin order for (a), (e) respectively. (c), (d), (g), (h) are the corresponding LDOS for energy range shown by dashed lines for (a), (e) respectively.

9. C-C bond length in carbon chains

Figure S40. Changes in the C-C bond length between carbon atoms in even (a) and odd (b) numbered chains connected to different electrodes with 5 and 6 membered terminal rings.

10. Transport properties of junctions with two parallel carbon chains

Figure S41. Comparison between transport properties of junctions with single odd (a) and even (b) carbon chains with that of two parallel even-even (c), odd-odd (d) and odd-even (e) carbon chains.

To understand the effect of two carbon chains between the electrodes, we also performed calculations using combinations of chains of different lengths: odd / odd, even / even, and odd / even and compared them to the individual odd or even chains, as shown in Figure S41. The conductance increases slightly in the junction with two parallel even-numbered chains compared to that with only one even-numbered chain. If two odd-numbered chains are connected in parallel, the spin polarisation that was observed for the single odd-numbered chain is not present in the two odd-numbered chains. As a result, the conductance of two odd-numbered chains is slightly lower than that of the single odd-numbered chain. Interestingly, the resulting conductance with a parallel connection of odd and even chains is higher than with a single even-numbered chain, but lower than with a single odd-numbered chain. The latter is due to the larger electrode / electrode distance in the junction with odd and even numbered chains.

11. Total energy differences between junctions with antiferromagnetically aligned and ferromagnetically aligned edges

	ΔE (eV)		
	-9.11		
	-14.73		
	-9.46		
	-16.6		
	-9.85		
	-14.87		
	-9.7		
	-15.15		
	-2.61		
	-3.2		
	-2.35		
	-1.81		

Figure S42. Total energy differences between junctions with antiferromagnetically aligned and ferromagnetically aligned edges suggest that antiferromagnetic aligned is favored energetically.